

THE EFFECT OF FIBER MISALIGNMENT ON PARAMETER DETERMINATION USING PICTURE FRAME TEST

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a hyperelastic model is used to investigate the effect of possible fiber misalignment during constitutive parameter identification using the picture frame test. The model utilizes a phenomenological invariant-based approach, in which no assumption is made concerning fiber extensibility. The test kinematics are first developed in full generality based on two transformations: the trellis and the enlargement, corresponding to the shear and fiber-stretch modes, respectively. Subsequently, a set of test data from bias extension, picture frame, and uniaxial extension experiments on twill 2x2 fabric is employed to identify the model parameters. In doing so, the effect of fiber misalignment is first neglected. Then, arbitrary fiber misalignment is included within the identification process, such that the stretch in the fiber directions is accounted for. Eventually, by comparison of these two, the effect of fiber misalignment on parameter determination using the picture frame test is concluded.

(Key terms: trellis and uniaxial tests; fiber misalignment; constitutive model)

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerical simulation of forming processes such as stamping is an important means for material selection, tool design, and process optimization. A critical component of simulation, however, is an accurate material constitutive model, which describes the response of the material under possible states of deformation. The accuracy, in turn, is linked to the techniques applied for determining parameters appearing in the models. Parameters are usually determined using simple but standardized tests. For this purpose, a number of tests have been recognized for the large deformation behavior of fiber reinforced textile composites. Among these, the bias extension, picture frame, and uniaxial extension tests are prominent examples. The first two, in particular, have been designed to produce a trellis in-plane shearing mode in flat pre-consolidated composite specimens, whereas the uniaxial extension test is mainly attributed to the evaluation of longitudinal properties in reinforcement directions.

Using these tests for parameter determination, material incompressibility and fiber inextensibility are often assumed. The former assumption is a reliable, though, not certain, assumption. In contrast, however, the consequence of constraining the extensional deformation of fibers is not

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widely understood, even if such extensibility is quite small. The alignment of specimens, especially in the picture frame test, is a practical problem such that even a slight fiber misalignment may result in different response beyond the Pin-Joined-Net (PJN) deformation [1-5]. If fibers are perfectly aligned, then the fabric is often modeled by the PJN approximation, in which fiber tows are fixed at crossover points, rotating freely about these points, without stretch. In the presence of any misalignment, fiber tows adopt a different angle from the frame angle and, thus, may stretch on either side of the crossover points. Moreover, depending on the strain rate, sample dimensions and constraints on deformation, occasionally the fiber slippage, accompanied by an immediate wrinkling/buckling, may also add to the above departure. In this work, we investigate the effect of fiber misalignment in the picture frame test on the effect of parameter determination. To this end, the fiber stretch (extension) within the picture frame test configuration will be determined first, and then a hyperelastic constitutive relationship will be developed and used to determine the response without neglecting the fiber misalignment.

2. EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE

In essence, the bias extension and the picture frame tests are both utilized to determine in-plane shear response of woven fabrics and should, therefore, lead to the same material parameters. However, unfortunately, because of the combined effect of shear, tension and slip during the deformation, a considerable difference between the responses of material from the two tests is often observed. To scrutinize this discrepancy, in this work both the bias extension and picture frame tests were conducted at 170°C with a crosshead rate of 162 mm/min. All tests were performed with the 1485 g/cm² (44 oz/yd²) twill 2x2 fabric made with commingled yarns of PP and glass-fibers commercialized by Vetrotx Certaineed Inc. under the trade name TWINTEX TM. Figure 1 shows the specimen employed in each test.

Figure 1: Schematic of specimen used in (a) bias-extension and (b) picture frame tests.

The initial width and length of the specimen in the bias extension test were selected as $W=88.9$ mm and $H=306.07$ mm. Because of constraints from the grips, the bias-extension specimen exhibits several deformation zones. A schematic of these zones before and after deformation is illustrated in Figure 2. In practice, the effective length of the specimen along which the trellis deformation occurs is only a fraction of the total length. In order to find this fraction a recent work [5] has provided a theoretical expression as: $L_{eff} = X_{be} - W$, where X_{be} is the total length. Accordingly, the effective length of the specimen in the undeformed state may be given

by: $L_{eff}^0 = H - W$, which for our case leads to approximately 70% of the initial length. For this test, in addition to the measurement of force vs. displacement, the corresponding fiber angle, ϕ , was monitored using a high-speed video camera. The measurement results are shown in Figure 3a, along with the angle change computed using the PJN assumption, where $\text{Cos } \phi = \mu_1 \text{Cos } \phi_0$, and μ_1 denotes the axial stretch ratio [1,6]. Reasonable consistency between the measured and computed angle change is noted, indicating likelihood of the pure trellis mode during the bias extension test.

For the picture frame test, flat consolidated plaques made from one ply of fabric were cut to obtain the specimens which were clamped between steel fixtures and bolted over the picture frame apparatus with three bolts per bar. Accordingly, the bar length was selected 152.4 mm, with the effective (deforming) fabric test area initially 139.7 mm x 139.7 mm. The measurement results are shown in Figure 3b.

Figure 2: Different deformation zones in bias-extension test.

Figure 3: Measurement results from (a) bias extension and (b) picture frame tests.

In comparison to the bias extension test, the picture frame test exhibits load values of much higher magnitude, even though the effective fabric area for both tests is comparable. As noted

previously, this difference is postulated to be due to the contribution of tensile loading of high modulus fibers within the picture frame test. Fiber yarns, indeed, inside the picture frame apparatus are directly constrained on the edges and so even a small amount of misalignment can yield a significant contribution to the fiber stretching. To justify this more adequately, uniaxial tension tests were performed using the same set up as in the bias extension test but with fiber yarns at 0 and 90 degrees with the loading direction. The initial length and width of the specimen were selected 222.25 mm and 88.9 mm, respectively. The load and nominal stress vs. stretch is shown in Figure 4. As can be seen in the figure, even small values of stretch result in large values of load, which could well support the earlier indication.

Figure 4: Measurement results from uniaxial extension test.

3. KINEMATICS INCLUDING FIBER MISSALIGNMENT

For the picture frame test configuration material and spatial Cartesian systems can be taken as shown in Figure 5. Accordingly, assuming a continuum manifold, the relationship between a material point in the reference configuration (\mathbf{P}) and its mapping $\mathbf{p} = \chi(\mathbf{P})$ in the current configuration is written as [7]:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} x_1 &= X_1 \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} + X_2 \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} \\ x_2 &= X_1 \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} + X_2 \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \\ x_3 &= h X_3 \end{aligned} \right. \quad (1)$$

Note that the through-thickness stretch ratio (h) can be selected based on the incompressibility of the material as follows. Using Eq. (1), the deformation gradient becomes

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} & \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} & 0 \\ \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} & \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

and with the incompressibility assumption ($\det(\mathbf{F}) = 1$) yields $h = \sec \gamma$. The Lagrangian strain tensor is then given by:

Figure 5: Coordinate systems employed in picture frame test.

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I}) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sin \gamma & 0 \\ \sin \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tan^2 \gamma \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Recalling that the convective derivative of a time-dependent physical quantity is the partial time derivative (local derivative) of its material representation, the rate of Lagrangian strain tensor can be given as

$$\dot{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \cos \gamma & 0 \\ \cos \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \tan \gamma \sec^2 \gamma \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3.1 SHEAR ANGLE

According to the geometry of the picture frame (assuming a rigid four-linkage mechanism), if the displacement at the end of the frame is denoted by d , and the length of each bar by L_{bar} , one can relate the displacement, d , to the shear angle, γ , by

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d + \sqrt{2} L_{bar}}{2 L_{bar}} \right) \quad (5)$$

3.2 FIBER MISALIGNMENT

Considering an arbitrary direction $\mathbf{n}_0 = \langle \cos \delta, \sin \delta, 0 \rangle$ in the reference configuration and using the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor, $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$, the square of stretch in that direction is given by:

$$\lambda_\delta^2 = \mathbf{n}_0 \mathbf{C} \mathbf{n}_0 = 1 + \sin \gamma \sin 2\delta \quad (6)$$

If fibers are perfectly aligned with the frame (see also Figure 5), i.e., $\alpha = 0$ & $\beta = 90^\circ$, then Eq. (6) yields: $\lambda_\alpha = \lambda_\beta = 1$. As such, the PJN approximation is suitable to characterize the (pure) trellis behavior of the material. However, if initially the weft- and warp-fibers are misaligned at arbitrary angles of α and β , respectively, then the stretch in these structural directions is no longer unity and instead is specified by

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_\alpha = (1 + \sin \gamma \sin 2\alpha)^{0.5} \\ \lambda_\beta = (1 + \sin \gamma \sin 2\beta)^{0.5} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Note that these stretches are imposed on the test material via the clamping edges, following the misalignment in the reference configuration. Under this condition, besides the *trellis* transformation represented by Eq. (1), the *enlargement* transformation of material points along the fiber directions should also be accounted for by means of Eq. (7). It should be noted that while the frame moves forward the stretch in the fiber direction also increases monotonically, as shown in Figure 6. Consequently, even though such extensibility is small, it can result in a considerable increase in load magnitude owing to the very high modulus of fiber materials. In other words, in the presence of misalignment the applied load should not only carry the trellis deformation of the material but also stretch the misaligned fibers.

At this point, in order to characterize the material under the above kinematics, the task turns to development of a constitutive model presenting stress components as a function of material constants and strain components. Afterwards, using a set of experimental data, material parameters are determined by employing an appropriate characterization procedure.

Figure 6: Theoretical variation of fiber stretch at different misalignments.

4. CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

The phenomenological invariant-based or hyperelastic constitutive approach suggests postulating the strain energy potential as a function of invariants of deformation. If two families of fibers in two structural directions \mathbf{a}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 reinforce an isotropic matrix material, according to [8] the set of invariants can be recognized as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Set of invariants for composite materials with two families of fibers.

Matrix material	$I_1 = \text{tr } \mathbf{C} \quad ; \quad I_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\text{tr } \mathbf{C} \right)^2 - \text{tr } \mathbf{C}^2 \right] \quad ; \quad I_3 = \det \mathbf{C}$
First family of fibers	$I_4 = \mathbf{a}_0 \mathbf{C} \mathbf{a}_0 \quad ; \quad I_5 = \mathbf{a}_0 \mathbf{C}^2 \mathbf{a}_0$
Second family of fibers	$I_6 = \mathbf{b}_0 \mathbf{C} \mathbf{b}_0 \quad ; \quad I_7 = \mathbf{b}_0 \mathbf{C}^2 \mathbf{b}_0$
Interactions	$I_8 = (\mathbf{a}_0 \mathbf{b}_0) \mathbf{a}_0 \mathbf{C} \mathbf{b}_0 \quad ; \quad I_9 = (\mathbf{a}_0 \mathbf{b}_0)^2$

Note that \mathbf{a}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 are defined in the reference configuration as: $\mathbf{a}_0 = \langle \text{Cos } \alpha, \text{Sin } \alpha, 0 \rangle$, $\mathbf{b}_0 = \langle \text{Cos } \beta, \text{Sin } \beta, 0 \rangle$. Accordingly, the invariant I_9 is a *constant* throughout the deformation and, therefore, the total free energy function can be postulated by $W = W(I_k; k = 1, \dots, 8)$ through the remaining eight independent invariants. Having postulated W , the components of (symmetric) second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor are expressed as

$$S_{ij} = 2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial C_{ij}} = 2 \sum_{k=1}^8 \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_k} \right) \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial C_{ij}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Taking into account the decoupled contribution of fibers and matrix, and neglecting the higher order terms of fiber deformation, one may take the free energy function (defined per unit reference volume) to be: $W = W_{\text{Matrix}}(I_1, I_2, I_3) + W_{\text{Fibers}}(I_4, I_6)$. Since the material is also assumed to be incompressible, i.e., $I_3 = \det \mathbf{C} = (\det \mathbf{F})^2 = 1$, then W_{Matrix} is only a function of the remaining matrix invariants I_1, I_2 . Note that hydrostatic pressure should then be determined solely from the equilibrium equations and boundary conditions. Under this condition, and given the mechanically identical family of fibers, the free energy function can be selected as [9]

$$W = \left[\frac{c_1}{2} (I_1 - 3) + \frac{c_2}{2} (I_2 - 3) \right] + \left[\frac{k_1}{2k_2} \{ \exp[k_2 (I_4 - 1)^2] - 1 \} + \frac{k_1}{2k_2} \{ \exp[k_2 (I_6 - 1)^2] - 1 \} \right] \quad (9)$$

where c_1 & c_2 are the matrix material parameters, and k_1 & k_2 are the fiber material parameters. Substituting the above energy function into Eq. (8) and assuming a state of plane stress, after a tedious but straightforward calculation, the shear stress in the reference configuration takes on the decoupled form given in Eq (10).

$$S_{12} = \left[c_1 \sin \gamma \sec^4 \gamma + c_2 \sin \gamma (2 \sec^4 \gamma - 1) \right] + k_1 \sin \gamma \left[\sin^2 2\alpha \exp(k_2 \sin^2 \gamma \sin^2 2\alpha) + \sin^2 2\beta \exp(k_2 \sin^2 \gamma \sin^2 2\beta) \right] \quad (10)$$

It should be noticed that as an active constraint within the test configuration, $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 90^\circ]$ ensuring that the fibers cannot be subjected to compressive strains ($\lambda_\alpha, \lambda_\beta \geq 1$).

5. FORCE RESPONSE PREDICTION

In the picture frame test, the direct calculation of stress values from measured force values may not be straightforward owing to the complex configuration and boundary conditions. In order to cope with this complexity, reference [7] has introduced a method by means of the principle of virtual work. In this so-called ‘*power method*’, the stress power induced into the material is equated to the rate of work of the forces acting on the bars of the picture-frame apparatus. Employing this principle in the reference configuration, and assuming a uniform deformation throughout the sheet, it follows that:

$$F d = S_{ij} E_{ij} \Omega \quad (\text{summation on } i, j) \quad (11)$$

where Ω is the deforming (inner) material volume in the reference configuration. We can then write: $\Omega = L_{in}^2 T$, where T is the thickness of the specimen. Accordingly, assuming a locally orthotropic fabric¹ with symmetry of misalignment (i.e., $\beta = 90 - \alpha$), the combination of Eqs. (4), (5), (10), and (11) delivers the following closed form equation giving the force response of the fabric, in terms of the shear angle.

$$F = \left(\frac{L_{in}^2 T \sin 2\gamma}{2L_{bar} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\gamma}{2}\right)} \right) \left[c_1 \sec^4 \gamma + c_2 (2 \sec^4 \gamma - 1) + 2k_1 \sin^2 2\alpha \exp(k_2 \sin^2 \gamma \sin^2 2\alpha) \right] \quad (12)$$

6. CHARACTERIZATION PROCEDURE: RESULTS

In order to investigate the effect of possible misalignment within the picture frame test, material parameters (c_1, c_2) are obtained from the bias extension test where good agreement with the pure trellis deformation had been found. This, in turn, supports the idea that the original shear parameters c_1, c_2 should be independent of fiber stretch mode. Subsequently, we employed Eqs. (8) & (9) for the bias extension test configuration and fitted the data of Figure 3a for the early stage of deformation so as to avoid the effect of yarn compaction. As a result, the constants c_1 and c_2 were found to be 0.15 MPa and -0.007 MPa, respectively. Next, in a similar manner we used the uniaxial test data of Figure 4 in order to select the appropriate fiber material parameters k_1 and k_2 . The reasoning is that in such a test the total load acting on the fabric is almost entirely

¹ i.e., when the two families of fibers are mechanically equivalent (see also [10]).

sustained by the fibers parallel to the loading direction. Consequently, the constants k_1 and k_2 were found to be 17.12 MPa and 1298.02, respectively. In both cases the free stress boundary condition was superimposed onto the inverse analysis, enhancing the accuracy of parameter determination. The obtained material parameters from these two tests are then used to predict the material response of the picture frame test as well. Initially, we neglect the effect of possible misalignment within the frame ($\alpha = 90 - \beta = 0^\circ$), and using Eq. (12) plot the force response as shown in Figure 7 (0°). The discrepancy with the experimental results is quite significant.

Figure 7: Prediction of material response for different degrees of fiber misalignment.

Next, we use the same model, but including arbitrary degrees of (symmetrical) fiber misalignment. The new predictions show that, even though small, fiber misalignment can significantly affect the material response during the rhomboid deformation of the frame. Clearly, after taking into account such a misalignment, the model shows good agreement with the experimental data for an original misalignment of approximately 1.5 degrees, well within experimental error [2]. Referring to Figure 6, this misalignment corresponds to a maximum of 2% fiber stretch, which is the range observed in the uniaxial test. Note that the degree of misalignment considered here is an *average* value. In practice, however, the fiber tows may initially be curvy and, thus, those which were not uniformly spaced and straight are first realigned then stretched during the deformation. Figure 7 suggests that the exact amount of misalignment is a critical issue for determination of model parameters using the picture frame test data (e.g., only 0.5 degrees difference of misalignment is enough to cause a significant divergence). If reliably known, then the fiber material parameters can be selected directly from the picture frame test. Otherwise, one possible solution is to acquire shear and extensional material parameters from the bias extension and uniaxial tests, and then fit the data of the picture frame test for various values of misalignment. Needless to say, more accurate identification work is needed to include the effect of fiber locking and, thus, possible slip and buckling mechanisms during the trellising deformation.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The combined effect of shear, tension, slip and buckling during the deformation of woven fabrics has brought researchers to a critical point in the characterization of such materials. Among these

modes of deformation, tension as a consequence of initially misaligned fibers demonstrates an important effect in the response of such materials during the picture frame test. Pursuant to the results of this paper, the inclusion of fiber misalignment in parameter determination using the picture frame test can be a vital key. If not adequately considered, the shear parameters may be influenced by the fiber tension, and are, therefore, no longer reliable for other deformation modes. However, it is understandable that the exact measurement of fiber misalignment within the frame may not be practical. Accordingly, it is suggested to acquire more accurate shear and extensional parameters from the bias extension and uniaxial tests where, respectively, the pure trellis and pure tension are more likely. Using these parameters, the prediction of material response, as well as a reasonable range of fiber misalignment, throughout the picture frame deformation should be practical.

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